

Identification of the Culprit Vessels Involved in Acute Inferior Wall Myocardial Infarction using Electrocardiography

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: India has reportedly shown the highest burden of acute coronary syndromes in the world. The ECG is the easiest and useful tool in the identification and management of acute MI. In inferior wall MI lesion is present in left circumflex artery and right coronary artery. In involvement of left circumflex artery ecg changes are ST-segment elevation in one lateral lead (V5, V6, or aVL) with an isoelectric or elevated ST segment in lead I and in involvement of right coronary artery ecg changes are ST-segment elevation in lead III greater than that in lead II. Early diagnosis and prediction of the culprit vessel helps in identifying the patients in whom aggressive reperfusion strategy is needed. When both the RCA and LCX are occluded then deciding which the culprit vessel is for acute MI is difficult and many a times angioplasty done on a chronic lesion and the acute occlusion was missed. In such circumstances, ECG is helpful in predicting the culprit artery.

Aim: To assess the value of ECG in predicting culprit vessels in acute inferior wall MI and correlating with coronary angiogram findings.

Objective: To evaluate sensitivity and specificity of ECG criteria in identification of culprit vessels in acute inferior wall Myocardial Infarction.

Study Design: Prospective observational study.

Methodology: Cases of Acute inferior wall MI diagnosed by ECG and Cardiac enzymes in patients aged more than 18 years admitted to tertiary care hospital are taken in study according to inclusion and exclusion criteria. Brief history was taken in each case following admission with reference to symptoms like chest pain and or dyspnoea, and the presence of risk factors like diabetes, hypertension, smoking and alcohol. A 12 lead ECG was done at admission and troponin I level was done in all patients admitted to the hospital. Then these patients were followed up after CAG (coronary angiography) and occluded vessel in angiography and patient's ecg changes were compared. All the above data were collected and recorded in a standard proforma.

Result: Total 70 patient of inferior wall MI were included in study as per inclusion and exclusion criteria. out of that 57 patients were male and 13 were females. Maximum number of patients was between age 51-60 years of age group. Out of total patient 26 patient have addiction of smoking. Out of total 70 patient 51 patient had left circumflex lesion in coronary angio from which in 27 patient also had changes of LCX involvement in ecg (true positive - sensitivity 52%). Out of 70 patient 57 patient had right coronary artery involvement in coronary angio from which 43 patient had changes of RCA involvement in ECG (true positive - sensitivity 75.43%). Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV of the ECG in identifying RCA occlusion were 75.43%, 100%, 100%, 48.14% respectively and Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV of the ECG in identifying LCX occlusion were 52%, 100%, 100%, 44.18% respectively. From 70 patient 11 patient were thrombolysed with inj. tenecteplase, 53 patients were thrombolysed with inj. streptokinase and in 6 patients inj. heparin was given and after cag stent placement in LCX done in 20 patients, rca stent placement done in 27 patients ,stent placement in RCA + LCX done in 11 patient.

Conclusion: In the present study we conclude that the ECG was found to be a sensitive and specific tool in identifying the involved coronary artery in acute inferior ST elevation MI and gives important information to guide management and to determine the prognosis of patients. So in rural area where facilities are not available, on admission ecg can help in diagnosing patient that can receive early thrombolysis therapy and further help in diagnosing patients who are at a high risk of developing complication which can be further shifted to higher center as early as possible.

Keywords: ECG, Inferior wall MI, culprit artery, RCA, LCX, coronary angiography.

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Introduction

In an adult ED population with acute chest pain, nearly 15% of patients will have an acute coronary syndrome. Worldwide from all deaths 30% were due to cardiovascular disease of which more than half are caused by coronary heart disease.[1] India has shown the highest burden of Acute coronary syndromes in the world. Patients in India who have acute coronary syndromes have a higher rate of STEMI than do patients in developed countries. Since most of these patients are poor, they are less likely to get evidence-based treatments and had greater 30-day mortality.[2] The electrocardiogram is the easiest and most used in the identification and management of acute myocardial infarction. Acute risk stratification in myocardial infarction is based on simple clinical parameters; laboratory markers and 12 lead electrocardiography. The electrocardiogram has been a primary screening.[3]

Inferior wall MI can result from occlusion of the left circumflex artery or the right coronary artery. In an inferior wall MI, ECG changes of ST-segment elevation in at least one lateral lead (V5, V6 or aVL) with an isoelectric or elevated ST segment in lead I is strongly suggestive of a left circumflex lesion (image A). And ECG changes of ST-segment elevation in lead III greater than that in lead II is suggestive of a right coronary artery occlusion (image B). When accompanied by ST-segment elevation in V1 or a V4R, it predicts a proximal right coronary artery lesion with accompanying right ventricular infarction, demonstrated by right-sided ECG leads. RV infarction associated with inferior infarction has higher morbidity than isolated inferior infarction.[4],[5],[6].

Figure 1: A - ST segment elevation in leads II,III,aVF as well as lead V6,ST depression in leads V1,v2,v3 reflecting reciprocal changes in the anterior leads. The patient was found to have 100% occlusion of left circumflex artery at cardiac catheterization

Figure 1: B - ST segment elevation in lead III greater than in lead II plus ST segment depression of >1 mm in lead I and lead aVL. The patient was found to have 100% occlusion of right coronary artery at cardiac catheterization.

*Images were taken from Tintinalli’s emergency medicine A comprehensive study guide.

Occlusion of the RCA, especially when involving the right ventricle, may have severe hemodynamic complications associated with increased risk of death, shock and arrhythmias. Management and prevention of these complications may be facilitated by early recognition of RCA involvement.

Early diagnosis and prediction of the culprit artery helps identifying the patient who requires early reperfusion treatment. Coronary arteriography is the best modality to determining the culprit artery in acute inferior wall MI. When both the RCA and LCX are involved, deciding which is the culprit vessel can be difficult, so many times angioplasty done on a chronic lesion while the acute occlusion which leads to MI was missed. In such circumstances having an independent predictor of the culprit artery like ECG is helpful.

Hence, the present study was done to evaluate the sensitivity and specificity of ECG in identification of culprit vessels in inferior wall MI.

Thrombolytic therapy for patients with acute MI improves the infarct coronary artery patency, limits AMI size, and improves left ventricular function and survival. With the advent of intervention aimed at limiting MI size, it becomes important to assess the amount of ischemic myocardium in the early phase of Acute MI, and to develop noninvasive methods for evaluation of these therapies.

Aim: To assess the value of ECG in predicting culprit artery in acute inferior wall MI and correlating with coronary angiogram findings.

Objective: To evaluate sensitivity and specificity of ecg criteria in identification of culprit vessels in acute inferior wall Myocardial Infarction.

Methodology:

Study Design: prospective observational study

Inclusion Criteria:

- Chest pain or discomfort lasting more than 30 minutes
- ECG showing ST elevation in lead 2,3,and aVF (inferior wall leads)
- Elevation of cardiac enzymes (Trop I)

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with history of Previous myocardial infarction,
- ECG showing st elevation in leads that suggestive of other than inferior wall mi,
- Prior CABG,
- Congenital heart disease,
- Clinical and ECG features suggestive of Pericarditis,
- Patients who do not agree to undergo coronary angiogram,
- Refusal to give consent.

Methodology:

Cases of Acute inferior wall MI diagnosed by ECG and Cardiac enzymes in patients aged more than 18 years admitted to tertiary care hospital are taken in study according to inclusion and exclusion criteria. Brief history was taken in each case following admission with reference to symptoms like chest pain, dyspnoea and other symptoms, and the presence of risk factors like diabetes, hypertension, smoking and alcohol. A 12 lead ECG was done at admission and troponin I level was done in all patients admitted to the hospital. Then these patients were followed after CAG (coronary angiogram) and correlation between ECG changes and angiography findings were done. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value for ecg(primary bedside point of care tool) in identifying culprit vessels were calculated in comparison to coronary angiography findings(gold standard investigation)All the above data were collected and recorded in a standard proforma.

ECG findings for inferior ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (ST elevation in lead 2,3,aVF and following changes)

Table 1:

ECG changes	culprit vessel
ST-segment elevation in lead III greater than in lead II plus ST-segment depression of >1 mV in lead I, lead aVL, or both	Right coronary artery
Absence of the above findings plus ST-segment elevation in leads I, aVL, V5, and V6 and ST-segment depression in leads V1, V2, and V3	Left circumflex coronary artery

Sensitivity: The ability of the test to detect all those with disease in the screened population
 Sensitivity = True Positive / True Positive + False Negative

Specificity: The ability of the test to identify correctly those free of disease in the screened population.

Specificity = True Negative / True Negative + False Positive

Positive Predictive Value: The likelihood that a person who has a positive test results does have the disease.

Positive Predictive Value = True Positive / True Positive + False Positive

Negative Predictive Value = True Negative / True Negative + False Negative

Negative Predictive Value:

The likelihood that a person who has a negative test results does not have the disease.

Observation:**Table 2: Distribution among Gender**

Male	Female	Total
57(81.42%)	13(18.57%)	70

In the presenting study out of total 70 patients 57 were male and 13 were female.

Table 3: Distribution among Age

Age	Total Patient
19-30	2 (2.8%)
31-40	4(5.71%)
41-50	11(15.71%)
51-60	23(32.85%)
61-70	18(25.71%)
71-80	9(12.85%)
81-90	3(4.28%)

Out of total 70 patients maximum number of patient with inferior wall mi presented to emergency room are from age group of 51-60 years.(23 patients)

Table 4: Comorbid Condition

Comorbidity	No of Patient
Hypertension	18(25.71%)
Diabetes Mellitus	28 (40%)
Hypothyroidism	7 (10%)
Other	10(14.28%)
Nil Comorbidity	7(10%)

Out of 70 patients 18 had hypertension, 28 had diabetes,7 had hypothyroidism,10 patients had other comorbidity like history of cva, dyslipidemia, obesity and 7 patients had no any comorbidity condition.

Table 5: Addiction

Addiction	No of Patient
Smoking	26 (37.14%)
Tobacco Chewer	17 (24.28%)
Alcoholic	6 (8.57%)
Nil Addiction	25 (35.71%)

We find that smoking is the major risk factor which leads to myocardial infarction in our study (37.14% of patients were smokers).

Table 6: Artery Involvement

Artery Involve	No Of Patient
Left Circumflex Artery	13 (18.57%)
Right Coronary Artery	19 (27.14%)
Lcx + Rca (Both Involve)	38 (54.28%)

There are 38 patients in whom both LCX and RCA arteries had lesions and 13 patients had lesions in LCX and 19 patients had lesions in RCA.

Table 7: Artery Involvement According To ECG in Which Angiography S/O Blockage of both Lcx and Rca

Artery Involved	No of Patients
No. Of Patient Having Ecg Suggestive Of Lcx Involvement (2,3,Avf St Elevation + One Of Lateral Lead / Avl /Lead V1 St Elevation)	14 (36.84%)
No. Of Patient Having Ecg S/O Rca Involvement (2,3,Avf St Elevation + Lead 3>2 St Elevation)	24 (63.15%)
Total Patient Having Both Artery Involvement According To Angiography	38

There are total 38 patients in whom angiography results were suggestive of both LCX and RCA involvement out of them 14 patients had ECG findings suggestive of LCX as culprit vessel and 24 patients had ecg findings suggestive of RCA as culprit vessel.

Table 8: Thrombolysis

Thrombolysis With Streptokinase	53 (75.71%)
Thrombolysis With Tenecteplase	11 (15.71%)
Heparinized	6 (8.57%)
Total	70

In my study from 70 patients, 53 patients were thrombolysed with inj. streptokinase , 11 patients were thrombolysed with inj. tenecteplase , 6 patients were heparinized.

Table 9: Artery in Which Stent Placement Done:

Artery	No Of Patient
Left Circumflex Artery (Lcx)	20 (28.57%)
Right Coronary Artery(Rca)	27 (38.57%)
Lcx + Rca	11 (15.71%)

After angiography stent placement in LCX done in 20 patients, stent placement in RCA done in 27 patients, stent placement in LCX and RCA both in 11 patients.

Table 10: Left Circumflex Artery Involvement

Ecg Criteria S/O Lcx Artery Involvement	Coronary Angiography S/O Lcx Lesion	Coronary Angiography S/O Lcx Lesion	
	Yes	No	Total
Yes	27 (True Positive)	0 (False Positive)	27
No	24 (False Negative)	19 (True Negative)	43
Total	51	19	70

Sensitivity of Lcx Involvement by ECG Criteria: 52%

Sensitivity = True Positive / True Positive + False Negative = 27/51 = 52%

Specificity of Lcx Involvement by ECG Criteria: 100% Specificity = True Negative / True Negative + False Positive = 19/19 = 100%

Positive Predictive Value: 100%

Positive Predictive Value = True Positive / True Positive + False Positive = 27/27 = 100%

Negative Predictive Value: 44.18%

Negative Predictive Value = True Negative / True Negative + False Negative = 19/43 = 44.18%

Table 11: Right Coronary Artery Involvement

Ecg Criteria S/O Rca Artery Involvement	Coronary Angiography S/O Rca Lesion	Coronary Angiography S/O Rca Lesion	
	Yes	No	Total
Yes	43 (True Positive)	0(False Positive)	43
No	14(False Negative)	13 (True Negative)	27
Total	57	13	70

Sensitivity of Rca Involvement by ECG Criteria: 75.43%

Sensitivity = True Positive / True Positive + False Negative = 43/57 = 75.43%

Specificity of Rca Involvement by ECG Criteria: 100%

Specificity = True Negative / True Negative + False Positive = 13/13 = 100%

Positive Predictive Value: 100%

Positive Predictive Value = True Positive / True Positive + False Positive = 43/43 = 100%

Negative Predictive Value: 48.14%

Negative Predictive Value = True Negative / True Negative + False Negative = 13/27 = 48.14%

Analysis and Discussions

Table 12: Distribution among Gender

	This study	Ruram JA et al. study	Shaikh Md. Shahidul Haque et al.
Male	57(81.42%)	86(86%)	152(82.16%)
Female	13(18.57%)	14(14%)	33(17.83%)
Total	70	100	185

In a study of Ruram JA et al. out of total patients 86% were male and 14% were female; in the study of Shaikh Md. Shahidul Haque et al. where out of 185 total patients 152(82.16%) were male and 33(17.83%) were female which is comparable to my study which has 81.42% male and 18.57% female.

Table 13: Distribution among Age

	This study	Ruram JA et al. study	Sibaram panda et.al.
19-30	2 (2.8%)	-	10 (9%)
31-40	4(5.71%)	16	14 (12.6%)
41-50	11(15.71%)	28	24(21.6%)
51-60	23(32.85%)	32	38(34.2%)
61-70	18(25.71%)	12	16(14.4%)
71-80	12(17.14%)	12	9(8.1%)
TOTAL	70	100	111

In my study the maximum number of patients were in the age group of 51-60 (23 patients), mean age +/- SD is 59.029 +/-12.15 which is comparable to the study of Ruram JA et al. where the maximum number of patients were in the age group 51-60 (no of patients - 32).[7] In my study the maximum number of patients were in the age group of 51-60 (23 patients) which is comparable to the study of Sibaram panda et.al. Where the maximum number of patients were in the age group 51-60 (no of patients - 38).

Table 14: Comorbid Condition

Comorbidity	This study	Shaikh Md. Shahidul Haque et al.	Chrysi koliaki et al
Hypertension	18(25.71%)	75(40.54%)	69.1%
Diabetes Mellitus	28 (40%)	84(45.40%)	28.3%

Table 15: Addiction

Addiction	This study	Shaikh Md. Shahidul Haque et al.	Chrysi koliaki et al
Smoking	26 (37.14%)	88(47.56%)	49%

According to a study done by the Shaikh Md. Shahidul Haque et al. found smoking 48%,diabetes 45% , hypertension 41% as risk factors for MI.[7]correlating with my study which has smoking 37.14%,diabetes 40%, hypertension 25.71% as risk factor. According to a study done by Chrysi koliaki et al found smoking 49%,diabetes 28.3% ,hypertension 69.1% as risk factors for MI.correlating with my study which has smoking 37.14%,diabetes 40% , hypertension 25.71% as risk factor.

Table 16: Artery Involvement

Artery Involve	This study	Shaikh Md. Shahidul Haque et al.	E Bayram and C Atalay et.al.
Left Circumflex Artery	13 (18.57%)	9(10.22%)	20(27.39%)
Right Coronary Artery	19 (27.14%)	37(42.04%)	15(20.54%)
Lcx + Rca (Both Involve)	38 (54.28%)	42(47.72%)	38(52.05%)
Total	70	88	73

According to a study done by E Bayram and C Atalay et.al. they found out of total 73 patients, 15 patients had RCA artery involvement and 20 patients had LCX involvement and a study done by Shaikh Md. Shahidul Haque et al. where they found out of 88 patient LCX blockage in 9, RCA blockage in 37,RCA + LCX blockage in 42 patients, where in my study out of total 70 patients 13 patients had LCX involvement,19 patients had RCA involvement and 38 patients had both RCA + LCX involvement in coronary angiography.[9]

Table 17: Thrombolysis

	This study	Ralf Zahn MD et.al.
Thrombolysis With Streptokinase	53 (75.71%)	50%
Thrombolysis With Tenecteplase	11 (15.71%)	16.6%

According to study by Ralf Zahn MD out of total patient's 50% were thrombolysed with streptokinase ,16.6% were thrombolysed with other thrombolytic agents and other remaining patient received primary angioplasty as treatment.^[10]which is correlated to my study in which 75.71% patients were thrombolysed by streptokinase,15.71% patients were thrombolysed by tenecteplase.

Table 18: Left Circumflex Artery Involvement

	This study	Ruram JA et. al.	D. Hasdai.et.al.
Sensitivity	52%	26%	83%
Specificity	100%	96%	96%
Positive Predictive Value	100%	86%	91%
Negative Predictive Value	44.18%	60%	93%

According to study Ruram JA et al. Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV of the ECG in identifying LCX occlusion were 26%, 96%, 86%, 60% respectively. Total patients taken in study were 100 from which 42 patients had inferior wall MI.[7] which is correlated to my study in which Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV of the ECG in identifying LCX occlusion were 52%, 100%,

100%, 44.18% respectively. According to study done by D. Hasdai et.al. Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV were 83%, 96%, 91%, 93% respectively[11] which is correlated to my study s/o Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV of the ECG in identifying LCX occlusion were 52%, 100%, 100%, 44.18% respectively.

Table 19:

	This study	E Bayram, C Atalay et.al.
Sensitivity	52	87
Specificity	100	100

According to study done by E Bayram and C Atalay et.al. in turkey they found Sensitivity, Specificity to found LCX occlusion by ecg criteria as 87% and 100% respectively [9]which is correlated to my study in which Sensitivity, Specificity of the ECG in identifying LCX occlusion were 52%,100% respectively.

Table 20: Right Coronary Artery Involvement

	This study	Ruram JA et al.	D.Hasdai.et.al.
Sensitivity	75.43%	78.5%	90%
Specificity	100%	100%	71%
Positive Predictive Value	100%	100%	94%
Negative Predictive Value	48.14%	75%	70%

According to study Ruram JA et al. Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV of the ECG in identifying RCA occlusion were 78.5%, 100%, 100%, 75%respectively.

Total patients taken in study were 100 from which 42 patients had inferior wall MI.[7]compare to this study in which Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV

of the ECG in identifying RCA occlusion were 75.43%, 100%, 100%, 48.14% respectively. According to study done by D. Hasdai et. al. Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV,NPV were 90%,7 1%, 94%, 70% respectively[11]compare to this study in which Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV,NPV of the ECG in identifying RCA occlusion were 75.43%, 100%, 100%, 48.14% respectively.

Table 21:

	This Study	E Bayram, C Atalay et. al.
Sensitivity	75.43%	86%
Specificity	100%	94%

According to study done by E Bayram and C Atalay et.al. in turkey they found Sensitivity, Specificity to found RCA occlusion by ECG criteria as 86% and 94% respectively ; compare to this study in which Sensitivity and Specificity to found RCA occlusion by ecg criteria as 75.43% and 100% respectively.[9]

Result

Total 70 patients of inferior wall MI were included in study as per inclusion and exclusion criteria. Out of that 57 patients were male and 13 were females. Maximum number of patients having MI is seen between ages 51-60 years. Out of total patient 26 patients had addiction to smoking. Out of total 70 patient 51 patients had left circumflex lesion in coronary angio from which in 26 patients also had changes of LCX involvement in ECG (true positive - sensitivity 52%). Out of 70 patient 57 patients had right coronary artery involvement in coronary angio from which 43 patients had changes of RCA

involvement in ECG (true positive - sensitivity 75.43%). Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV of the ECG in identifying RCA occlusion were 75.43%, 100%, 100%, 48.14%respectively and Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV of the ECG in identifying LCX occlusion were 52%, 100%, 100%, 44.18% respectively. From 70 patient 11 patient were thrombolysed with inj. tenecteplase , 53 patients were thrombolysed with inj. streptokinase and in 6 patient inj. heparin was given and after cag result stent placement in LCX done in 20 patients , rca stent placement done in 27 patients ,stent placement in RCA + LCX done in 11 patients.

Conclusion

On admission ECG in patients with acute ST elevation inferior wall myocardial infarction is valuable in early diagnosis and prediction of the culprit vessels which helps in identifying the patients in which aggressive reperfusion strategy is needed. When both the RCA and LCX are occluded then deciding which the culprit vessel is

for acute MI is difficult and many a times angioplasty done on a chronic lesion and the acute occlusion was missed. In such circumstances, ECG is helpful in predicting the culprit artery. In the present study we conclude that the ECG was found to be a sensitive and specific tool in identifying the involved coronary artery in acute inferior ST elevation MI and gives important information to guide management and to determine the prognosis of patients. So in rural area where facilities are not available, on admission ecg can help in diagnosing patients that can receive early thrombolysis therapy and further help in diagnosing patient who are at a high risk of developing complication which can be further shifted to higher center as early as possible.

Limitation of Study: Single center study, small sized samples, very short period of time.

Ethical Statement: Ethical permission was received from the institutional review board Smt. NHLMMC, Ahmedabad, Gujarat.

List of abbreviation: AMI: acute myocardial infarction, CAG: coronary angiography ED: emergency department, ECG: electrocardiography, LCX: left circumflex artery, MI: myocardial infarction, NPV: negative predictive value, PPV: positive predictive value, RCA: right coronary artery.

Data availability: Excel sheet with all data will be available with the corresponding author.

Author's Contributions: Dr Rujuta Teraiya, Dr Rajvi Dave, Dr Vipul Joliya has contributed to the Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, resources and writing (original draft). Dr Bhavesh Jarwani has contributed to supervision, validation, and writing (review and editing). All the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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